

SIMILES IN NAZAR ESHONQUL'S STORIES (IN THE EXAMPLE OF THE STORIES "UNOPENED DOOR", "HEART DUST" AND "COFFIN")

Faizullayeva Ezoza

Navoi State Pedagogical Institute 2nd year student of the
Faculty of Uzbek Language and Literature.

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Abstract: Similes not only perform a stylistic task in artistic works, but also indicate how strong the writer's artistic skills are. This article discusses the linguopoetic aspects of the similes used in Nazar Eshanqul's stories "The Opened Door" and "Coffin".

Key words: similes, methodological task, subject of simile; the standard of analogy; basis of analogy; The form of simile is the standard of simile.

Similes are one of the tools that have great artistic and stylistic potential in our speech, and ensure the expressiveness and attractiveness of the speech. Similes in works of art not only perform a methodological task, but also show how wide the imagination of the writer is. will give. Beginning with Panini's grammar (4th century BC), similes were studied as poetic figures in ancient Indian poetic-grammatical treatises and it was emphasized that similes consist of 4 regular elements, i.e.: 1) thing or subject to be compared; 2) something or an object similar to it; 3) simile sign; 4) a formal indicator of simile. In the Uzbek language, as in all other languages, similes consist of 4 elements, and we call them simile subject, simile benchmark, simile base, and simile form indicator. First of all, it should be noted that similes arise as a product of a specific figurative way of thinking. That is why they always have an artistic-aesthetic value in speech, they serve to ensure the emotional-expressiveness, expressiveness, and effectiveness of speech. 2 types of similes, namely: 1) individual-author similes or free similes; 2) universal or stable similes are distinguished. From the point of view of artistic and aesthetic value, free similes from the point of view of linguopoetic salmon occupy a special place in artistic speech as one of the means of showing the skill of the writer. The essence of stable similes is that the image expressed in the standard of simile is stabilized, such similes, although used by a specific person or creator, have struck in the language community over time. entered and stabilized as permanent expressions, took a place in the lexicon of the national language.

In the works of Nazar Eshanqul, similes are very effectively used as tools that reveal the artistic and aesthetic aspects of speech and ensure its effectiveness. Especially from individual-author similes. Below we present examples of such similes used by the author in the stories "The Unopened Door" and "The Coffin":

Every night, after landing on the tree where she was sitting for a while, the wife, like a hawk on a long journey, moves away from her day by day and goes to an unknown destination. She wept until the morning, remembering her inverted, rude, sarcastic character, the days of her wifehood, which once flew together with her husband, but now seemed like an abandoned destination of happiness. [2. Page 164] Kelinchak - "tree". The wife's husband, who is moving away day by day, is compared to a hawk, which after a while perched on the tree where it was sitting, went on a long journey. He will not return to this "tree". There is a time of womanhood that has passed. It is compared to the happiness that was abandoned in

its address. These similes are an impressive expression of the inner experiences and sufferings of the hero.

Sometimes she had nothing to do with her, sometimes suffering, peace, sometimes intensity, enthusiasm, happiness, the dark face of her husband, who was slowly extinguishing in the thick fog, was called to her, and gradually he could see the feeble reverence fading away without a trace. [2. page 165]

The daughter-in-law's waning respect for her (did she actually have one?) is compared to a slowly dying fire. When we approached the city, we saw that the gate, which looked like a huge wing of a huge creature, was as praised by the chief. [2. Page 181] The gate is an object of analogy; wing – the standard of analogy; big-the basis of analogy. Such an analogy embodies the beginning process of ugly and negative events in the student's mind.

Houses are purposely built upside down to keep the interior cool, and the dim light coming from the windows is not enough to illuminate the rooms. An example of an exhausted hero is lying in a corner. after [2. Page 184] This is a simplified artistic expression of the ugly, cold scene in the city through animation and simile.

Now, since the outbreak of the plague, our city has become devoid of grace, and at that time you thought that the city was a figment of imagination: elegant domes, silver paint, marbles like fragments of a delicate and passionate soul, columns that could support eternity, the eyes of a girl child. fountains of the same age - everything was beautifully combined. The author compares the beauty of the city - elegant domes, bright colors, marbles, columns that can support eternity to pieces of a delicate and passionate soul; the girl compares the purity of fountains to the tears of a child.

I saw that the head of the control had clenched his fist in anger, and he had a look on his face like a rabid bear that would destroy the whole city if he let go. The superintendent's intense anger was compared to a rabid bear. Who knows, maybe it's because I'm tired of reading a lot of different manuscripts, but like the sun bursting from the horizon, the long night is suddenly illuminated, the smile of your beloved girl is a word that lights up your tongue. words, metaphors, scenes and symbols have enlightened my heart. Here, the situation of the hero of the story not having read a mature manuscript for a long time is likened to the situation where the long night is suddenly illuminated by the sun rising from the horizon. The words, metaphors, scenes, and symbols in the work depict in strong emotional colors that the smile of your beloved girl brightens the heart.

In this manuscript, the events started suddenly, without explanation, without details, just like when a monster sneaks out in front of you while you are in a hurry. In this sentence, the beginning of the manuscript without any explanations and details, "as if it was scraped from the roof", reminds the hero of the story of a situation in which a predator has escaped in a hurry, but it was easier for him to convey to the reader an emotion stronger than a phrase through such a simile. My experiences at that time were depressing and hopeless, like the experiences of a person hanging on a tree alone in the endless sea after a shipwreck, and these pages were like a black rabbit that blew away the sparks of hope from the gardens of my heart. In this sentence, the writer was able to describe with the help of very strong emotional colors that the experiences of the hero of the story, who read the manuscript, were similar to the experiences of a person hanging on a tree alone in the vast sea.

The author's own similes are based on the author's own gaze, observation, artistic imagination, and the power of analogy are similes created without. In such similes, originality,

imagery and expressiveness is always clearly expressed. The purpose of any analogy is to concretize concepts that are difficult to imagine, abstract clarification of concepts, the subtlest aspects of events, actions, and situations can be seen embodied in beautiful colors before the eyes of the reader. We can conclude that the similes in Nazar Eshanqul's stories "The Opened Door" and "Coffin" are mainly individual-author similes used by the creator as a result of the skill of using words.

References:

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